

EU-RISE: Advancing European Space Robotics for a Future Commercial Ecosystem

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ABSTRACT

This paper details the European Robotics for Space Ecosystems (EU-RISE) project, an initiative funded by the European Union to advance robotic and autonomous technologies for in-space servicing, assembly, and manufacturing (ISAM). EU-RISE is structured around two key workstreams: a market-needs assessment to define future mission capabilities and the development of a modular architecture, and the adaptation and integration of hardware and software building blocks into a functional demonstrator. The paper provides a comprehensive overview of the system's hardware, including the Versatile In-Space and Planetary Arm (VISPA) and KUKA robotic manipulator as well as the

Multi-Purpose Tool (MPT). On the software front, it presents a multi-tier architecture, a robust digital twin, and the Robotic System Control (RSC) software for managing tasks and fault recovery [1]. By describing the interplay of these components, this paper highlights EU-RISE's contribution to a more autonomous, cost-effective, and reliable future for in-orbit infrastructure.

1. Introduction

The commercial and institutional roadmaps of major space agencies, including the European Space Agency (ESA), the European Union (EU), and national agencies like DLR and UKSA, increasingly emphasize the necessity of developing in-orbit capabilities. The space industry is undergoing a paradigm shift, moving away from mission-specific, single-use satellites towards a more sustainable and flexible ecosystem of on-orbit services (OOS), assembly (OOA), and manufacturing (OOM). This new paradigm, collectively referred to as In-Space Servicing, Assembly, and Manufacturing (ISAM), is crucial for fostering a robust European space economy and ensuring self-reliance in the deployment and maintenance of space-based infrastructure. The EU-RISE project directly addresses this need by focusing on the advancing space robotic technologies, as well as testing methodologies and facilities. The project is designed to overcome current limitations, such as a lack of standardized hardware and the immaturity of robotic flight software. By leveraging existing European building blocks and integrating them into a cohesive, end-to-end demonstrator, EU-RISE aims to strengthen Europe's competitiveness in the rapidly growing ISAM market.

This paper provides a comprehensive system description of the EU-RISE technologies and hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) demonstrator. It outlines the project's two core workstreams, detailing the market analysis that informs the system architecture and the subsequent development and integration of the key hardware and software components. The document is structured to present the physical designs and an overview of the software design, discuss the role of the ground control console and digital twin, and conclude with the project's overall contributions to the field of space robotics.

2. Mission and Market

The EU-RISE project addresses the ongoing transformation of space operations, where future missions will increasingly depend on autonomy, modularity, and sustainable practices. Traditional approaches are limited by high launch costs, constrained payload volumes, and the absence of in-orbit servicing or repair, restricting mission design and asset lifetime. EU-RISE seeks to enable a new space ecosystem defined by in-space servicing, assembly, and manufacturing (ISAM), where infrastructures can be adapted, extended, and reused to support activities ranging from transportation and logistics to recycling and production directly in orbit.

To achieve this vision, EU-RISE follows two complementary workstreams. The first focuses on market and mission analysis, assessing the evolution of future space ecosystems and identifying opportunities across agencies, industry, and commercial operators. It highlights the growing demand for services such as inspection, maintenance, refueling, assembly of large structures, and material reuse. A key outcome of this analysis is the recognition that such capabilities must be designed with modularity at their core. Modular building blocks—reconfigurable depending on the mission—offer the necessary flexibility to cover a broad range of applications while optimizing costs and reducing risks.

The second workstream builds directly on these findings by developing enabling technologies. Here, modular robotic building blocks are defined and integrated into an end-to-end demonstrator. Components such as robotic manipulators, vision systems, control units, tools, and standardized interfaces are combined to validate how modular systems can be configured to address diverse mission scenarios. This demonstrator not only proves the feasibility of modular ISAM architectures but also provides a tangible path toward future European capabilities in space robotics and automation.

The market landscape shows wide-ranging interest in ISAM. Space agencies view it as a means to extend the scope of scientific missions, support large infrastructures, and enhance orbital sustainability through debris mitigation and resource reuse. Commercial satellite operators seek to reduce operational costs via servicing and upgrades, while

insurers and manufacturers benefit from greater reliability and flexibility in spacecraft design. For military stakeholders, ISAM represents a strategic opportunity to strengthen resilience and adaptability in space operations.

By linking market requirements with technological development, EU-RISE establishes a foundation for Europe to federate its industrial ecosystem around a sovereign ISAM capability. In doing so, it strengthens competitiveness in a rapidly evolving global market while promoting sustainable, modular approaches that will define the future of space activities.

3. End-to-end demonstrator hardware

The physical design of the EU-RISE end-to-end demonstrator is built on a series of hardware building blocks that have been adapted and integrated to perform complex ISAM tasks.

The end-to-end demonstrator will be tested in two configurations, the servicer/host configuration and an in-orbit demonstration (IOD) configuration in a cargo trunk of the NYX platform or a similar spacecraft. Both configurations are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: End-to-End Demonstrator Configuration

The system is designed to be tested in a terrestrial laboratory, mimicking a space environment, and includes a testbed with a Gravity Offloading System

and a Motion Tracking System. The core hardware elements are as follows:

- Manipulator systems: two robotic arms shall perform the main robotic tasks. The VISPA, being developed by Airbus Defence and Space UK, and an industrial robotic manipulator, e.g. KUKA's "Leichtbauroboter" (LBR) iiwa, representing a function model of an additional space-qualified arm.
- Multi-purpose tools (MPTs): two robotic multi-purpose tools shall be attached to the manipulators and shall be used to pick-up different tool sockets depending on the specific task the robots have to perform.
- Tool-sockets are specific (mainly mechanical) elements that can be attached to the MPTs to add specific manipulation interfaces such that different objects can be grasped during operations. For EU-RISE two different tool sockets are foreseen: a cleat gripper.
- Tool-magazine is a specifically built structure to hold tool-sockets.
- Workbench is a two degree of freedom (DOF) manipulator built for carrying the parts during the assembly process in order to achieve better reachability of the assembled structure.
- Antenna reflector is composed of a breadboard structure made of already pre-assembled five sub-reflectors and an additional sub-reflector that will be manipulated by the robotic arms to demonstrate a representative antenna reflector assembly sequence.
- Assembly part-dispenser is a mechanical structure built for holding the sub-reflector elements of the antenna reflector.
- Antenna boom (equipped with a dummy feed element) is (mainly) a mechanical structure meant to mimic the functionality of an antenna feed, once correctly coupled with the assembled antenna reflector.
- Client spacecraft and refueling modules are mockups of a spacecraft and refueling modules providing the necessary structural elements to the client and servicer tanks that are to be used to demonstrate the transfer of fluid via a specialized refueling Standard Interface (RSIs) once the modules are rigidly connected to the client spacecraft.

3.1. Robotic Manipulators

The demonstrator utilizes two robotic arms:

- Airbus Versatile In-Space & Planetary Arm (VISPA): As a key component of the demonstration, the VISPA arm is a 6-DOF manipulator with a compact stowage envelope and an extended reach of approximately 2 meters. It is designed for zero-gravity environments, so its operation on the ground requires support from the Gravity Offloading System. The arm is controlled by an on-board computer via a CAN bus and is equipped with a force/torque sensor for compliant control during contact operations. The final manipulator can be seen during assembly as a flat configuration for functional testing in Fig. 2 and fully assembled in Fig. 3.

Figure 2: The VISPA robotic arm in a flat configuration for functional testing

Figure 3: The fully assembled VISPA robotic arm without end-effector

- KUKA iiwa R14 Industrial Robot: This commercial robot serves as a functional analog for a second robotic manipulator, enabling dual-arm manipulation scenarios to be tested. The KUKA arm is robust enough to operate under 1g conditions without offloading and is controlled by

a dedicated S/W component that communicates via UDP.

3.2. Multi-Purpose Tool (MPT) and Tool Sockets

The MPT is a central actuator and avionics unit designed to be a versatile end-effector. It interfaces with various tool sockets via a special SIROM version, allowing the robot to perform multiple operations without needing a full tool change.

Figure 4: The Multi-Purpose Tool (MPT) with the special SIROM interface for tool exchange based on the refuelling version.

The MPT itself contains a camera and illumination unit, and communicates with the Robotic Control Unit (RCU) via CAN bus. The tool sockets include:

- **Frame Gripper Socket:** Designed for grasping triangular frames, as found on the antenna sub-reflectors.
- **Cleat Gripper Socket:** Designed to grasp small, rounded objects using a combination of force and form fit, such as cleats for connecting sub-reflectors.
- **Wrench Socket:** Transfers torque from the MPT to tighten and loosen screws. It features functions for misalignment compensation, screw detection and rotational position detection, ensuring accurate automated operation.

The main advantages of the MPT approach is reduction of development time and costs associated with the tools. The mission specific tool sockets can be designed and tested rather fast as it is a pure mechanical mechanism without the need for actuator or

avionic development. In addition to this two factors the MPT architecture reduces the space required on a spacecraft or mobile robot if several tool functions are needed. The used tools for the EU-RISE project are depicted in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Wrench socket, Cleat Gripper and Frame Gripper Socket

3.3. Standard Interconnects (SIs) and Refueling System

Standard Interfaces (SIs) are critical for modularity and connecting different elements.

- **SIROM C:** A standard interface used for berthing and robotic services. It provides mechanical, data, power, and thermal coupling. In the demonstrator, it is used for the boom assembly.
- **SIROM G:** A specialized SI that includes a fluidic connection. This is the core component of the refueling demonstration, enabling the transfer of a liquid (distilled water) from a servicer tank to a client tank. The fluid transfer is controlled by relays that open and close valves.

3.4. Testbed and Workspace Mock-ups

The demonstrator's workspace, inspired by the NYX platform and a top panel configuration, includes a series of mock-ups to simulate the in-space environment:

Workbench: An active, 3-DOF platform that holds pre-assembled parts and can be oriented to a convenient position for assembly.

Antenna Reflector Kit: A mock-up of a large antenna to be assembled from triangular sub-reflectors.

Part Dispenser: A structure designed to hold and release the sub-reflector parts for robotic manipulation.

Transceiver Boom: A mock-up of an antenna boom that is assembled in front of the reflector to demonstrate the boom placement and its connection via a SIROM C interface.

Refuelling Demonstrator: The refueling demonstration is an optional but key part of the EU-RISE project that focuses on showcasing the capability of transferring fluid between two tanks in orbit. It utilizes specialized hardware, including two mock-up satellites: a servicer satellite with a pressurized tank of distilled water and a receiver satellite with an empty tank. The core technology is the SIROM G, a specialized Standard Interconnect (SI) that provides a fluidic connection in addition to mechanical and electrical links. The two elements consisting of a client satellite and a refuelling ORU are depicted below in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: The refuelling mock-up of the client satellite and the refuelling ORU to transfer fluid from the ORU to the client satellite.

The process involves a robotic arm grasping the servicer satellite and positioning it above the receiver satellite. Once the two are mated via the SIROM G, a sequence of valve controls, managed by the robotic software, is initiated to transfer the water. The demonstration aims to validate the fluid transfer capabilities and the use of the SIROM G for such in-orbit servicing tasks.

4. End-to-end demonstrator software

The demonstrator's software architecture is built on a multi-tier, hierarchical structure that orchestrates all robotic activities from high-level mission goals down to low-level hardware control. This architecture, known as the **Robotic System Control (RSC)**, is inspired by the ESA Functional Reference Model (FRM) [2] and NASA's NASREM [3] and is designed to be flexible and compatible with various on-board software frameworks [1].

Figure 7: The overall robotic software architecture

Figure 8: Mapping of the hardware and software elements of the end-to-end demonstrator

The RSC is composed of three main layers:

- **High-Level Behavior Controller (Level C):** This is the highest level of abstraction, where the mission is represented as a **behavior tree** [4]. This symbolic, task-oriented approach allows the system to dynamically adapt to mission requirements. The behavior controller evaluates the tree's nodes, which in turn trigger specific tasks at the intermediate level.
- **Intermediate Layer (Task Controller / Level B):** This layer acts as the bridge between the symbolic

mission plan and the physical world. It uses a script interpreter (e.g., JavaScript or MicroPython) to execute robotic tasks. These scripts resolve symbolic information, such as target poses and waypoints, from the **World Model Database** and dynamically changing data from the **Monitoring Controller** which collects and represents all telemetry data of the functional layer. These scripts finally perform numerical commands for the S/W components of the functional layer.

- **Functional Layer (Level A):** This is the lowest control layer, containing the hardware drivers and "intelligent skills" that interact directly with the physical system. It includes components such as:
 - **Arm Control S/W:** Generates and executes joint-space and Cartesian trajectories based on either pre-planned paths or high-level inputs, enabling position and force control of VISPA.
 - **Perception S/W:** Provides vision-based capabilities, including intrinsic and extrinsic camera calibration, marker detection, and object pose estimation.
 - **Motion Planning S/W:** Generates collision-free trajectories for the robotic arms based on the mission's goals and environmental constraints.
 - **H/W Drivers:** Low-level controllers for various hardware components, including the MPT, SIROMs, and the workbench.

Beyond this three-tiered structure, the RSC relies on several key system components:

- **World Model Database:** A central database that stores static mission data, such as trajectories, waypoints, and calibration information. It also manages dynamic transformations, providing a real-time representation of the scene for all software components.
- **Monitoring Controller:** This component collects and processes all telemetry and housekeeping data from the system's components. It performs crucial **Fault Detection, Isolation, and Recovery (FDIR)** by checking data against predefined limits and initiating a non-nominal control flow if a fault is detected.

The entire RSC framework is built on an abstraction layer that enables it to be deployed on different underlying frameworks, including **ROS2**, **ESA TASTE-10** [5], and **NASA cFS** [6], ensuring broad

compatibility and reusability. A more detailed description can be found in [1].

4. Arm Control

The arm controller enables VISPA to generate and execute trajectories based on pre-planned paths provided by a motion planner, or on high-level inputs such as user input or visual servoing. It also controls interaction with the environment in terms of applied forces/torques, accounting for errors/external disturbances within the system. The controller's main features are pre-processing and trajectory generation, task space control, joint space control, force control, and a CAN bus interface. The software is developed using MATLAB®/Simulink®, which allows for a model-based design approach to software development and the reuse of existing arm control software developed within Airbus Defence and Space. Furthermore, using these environments enables the software to be tested using multidomain simulation models before moving to hardware, and to be deployed onto the target platform by leveraging the code generation capabilities of MathWorks® software. Finally, if code certification is required, the generated software can be verified against standards such as ISO 26262 and DO-178C.

5. Ground Control and Digital Twin

The ground control and digital twin components are critical for mission preparation, validation, and execution. The architecture is designed to provide operators with comprehensive tools for interacting with both the simulated and physical systems.

5.1. Robotic Ground Console

The Robotic Ground Console acts as the primary interface for human operators.

Figure 9: Outline of the EU-RISE ground console: The full flight segment is represented by a copy of the flight S/W where H/W drivers are replaced by their corresponding I/Fs to the simulator.

It is a Python-based graphical prototypic user interface (GUI) that enables remote control and monitoring of the robotic system. Key functions of the ground console include:

- **Mission Preparation:** It features a behavior tree editor and a world model database editor, allowing operators to define and store mission-critical data and sequences.
- **Commanding:** The GUI provides a manual command interface for sending single commands to individual components, which is essential for debugging and testing.
- **Monitoring:** Operators can visualize real-time telemetry, including numerical data and camera images, through dedicated windows and diagrams.
- **ROS2 Bridge:** To ensure communication between the ground console and the various flight software frameworks, a ROS2 bridge is used. This component translates data and commands between the ROS2-based ground console and the specific middleware used by the flight segment (e.g. TASTE-10 or NASA's cFS). The RSC representation on the ground segment directly applies ROS2 as the underlying framework to establish compatibility with the rest of the ground console [1].

5.2. Digital Twin and Simulation

The digital twin is a high-fidelity virtual replica of the physical demonstrator. It plays a dual role in both the mission's preparatory and operational phases.

- **Mission Preparation:** During this phase, the digital twin is used to validate and verify mission

scenarios before they are executed on the physical hardware. It relies on a multi-body simulator, such as **Webots**, to create a realistic 3D environment with simulated actuators and sensors. The ground console can then be connected to this simulated environment to test behavior trees, tasks, and trajectories, ensuring they are collision-free and kinematically feasible.

- **Mission Execution:** The digital twin acts as a monitoring tool by receiving telemetry data from the real system during contact windows. This allows operators to visualize past operations, analyze plots of performance data, and compare the actual system state against the expected state. If an anomaly is detected, the digital twin can be used to simulate and test corrective actions before they are sent to the physical demonstrator. This capability is vital for robust fault detection, isolation and recovery (FDIR) and for ensuring mission continuity.

The digital twin is essentially a copy of the RSC flight software, with the hardware-specific functional layer components replaced by simulator interfaces. This ensures that the simulated system behaves as representatively as possible, providing a reliable platform for mission planning and validation.

6. Future Outlook

The EU-RISE project, while successfully integrating a complex robotic system, encountered to date several challenges that highlight key areas for future development in space robotics. The demonstrator serves as a vital proof-of-concept, but its transition to a flight-ready system requires further maturation of both hardware and software.

Future Outlook and Contributions

The EU-RISE project lays a strong foundation for future advancements of developed technologies.

Future work will focus on maturing the **Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs)** of the building blocks of the demonstrator as well as of the overall robotic system. This includes further refining the system's planning and control algorithms for robustness and accuracy, expanding the library of tasks

and behaviors to handle a wider range of missions, and integrating more advanced autonomy features. The project's hardware mock-ups and modular interfaces will continue to serve as a valuable blueprint for developing new **ISAM** capabilities, paving the way for a self-reliant and competitive European space ecosystem.

7. Conclusion

The EU-RISE project integrates and aims at validating a comprehensive robotic system for in-space servicing, assembly, and manufacturing. By addressing both the high-level needs of a future space ecosystem and the low-level technical challenges of robotic perception, planning and control, the project aims to demonstrate a viable path toward a more autonomous and sustainable in-orbit capabilities and infrastructure. The modular architecture, consisting of adaptable hardware building blocks and a flexible software framework, provides a foundation for future missions. The successful integration of a digital twin and a ground control console enables robust mission planning and validation, a critical step for increasing the reliability of complex space operations. In summary, EU-RISE aims to advance the European capabilities in space robotics by demonstrating a harmonized and highly integrated system that can serve as a blueprint for commercial and institutional applications.

9. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under the grant agreement No. 101134934. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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